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Educational commons spaces: communing practices as a way through conflict resolution

Joana R. Casanova, Natália Fernandes, Erika Machado, Teresa Sarmento
(CIEC –*Centro de Investigação em Estudos da Criança, Instituto de Educação
Universidade do Minho (Portugal)*)

Introduction: SMOOTH-Educational Commons and Active Social Inclusion (H2020,Ref.101004491) is a European project based on the emergent paradigm of the ‘commons’ as an alternative value and action system in education for children and young people. **Aims:** Researchers intend to analyze if ‘educational commons’ can operate as a catalyst for reversing inequalities through methods such as pedagogical documentation, pedagogy of active listening, ethnography, and discourse analysis. It proposes an innovative action-research program with and by children to 1)Reverse inequalities faced by children from vulnerable social groups; 2)Strengthen inter-cultural and inter-generational dialogue and social integration; 3)Develop vital social and personal skills for the children and adults; 4)Create smooth spaces of democratic citizenship and experimentation with new ways of thinking and doing based on equality, collaboration, sharing and caring. In this sense, to build and foster community through differences, it is relevant to understand the tensions/conflicts that emerge in children's everyday situations. **Method:** This work presents the project, particularly, one of the study cases, implemented at a severely disadvantaged context, at non-formal space of education in the north of Portugal, with children from 8-10 years old, from February-December 2022, two sessions a week for, in a total of 30 sessions. **Results:** It is analyzed along the sessions the emerging and manifestation of tensions, and conflict triggers for children, pointing to the frequency and the intensity of occurrence, and ways of children manage to thrive. It is observed the transformation in frequency, intensity, and resolution skills along the sessions, through mechanisms of strengthening children's voices, participation, and collaboration, and reinforcing their right to be part of important decisions in their life. **Conclusion:** Some reflections are pointed out about the challenges and strengths of the research-action project and its results considering the dimensions: children as commoners, communing practices and community & common good.

Keywords: Educational commons; children; active social inclusion.